

METHODOLOGY TO ADAPT LEARNING SCENARIOS TO AN INDUSTRY 5.0 PERSPECTIVE

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1. Introduction

Transitioning to Industry 5.0 (I5.0) requires businesses to rethink their cultures, strategies, and workforce skills. This new era emphasizes human-centric approaches, resilience, and sustainability, making it essential to adopt a tailored approach across different industries and groups[1]. However, identifying the specific skills needed for I5.0 remains difficult, slowing down its integration into companies. To address this, the Horizon Bridges5.0 project [2] focuses on adjusting training programs towards I5.0 requirements within learning ecosystems. The project identifies the main practices of the leading companies considered I5.0 in Europe and aligns education with the demands of those.

This article outlines the method's key steps and its application in diverse learning environments, offering a promising approach to bridge the education-industry gap in I5.0.

2. Case Presentation

Within the Bridges5.0 project we introduce a methodology to tailor training programs in learning ecosystems for I5.0 demands. The efficacy of this methodology will be tested in six learning ecosystems across Europe.

I5.0 is characterized as a multidimensional concept with various interacting pillars, as illustrated in Figure 1 [3]. Addressing the challenge of defining specific I5.0 skills arising from these interactions, the methodology emphasizes the **organizational practices of I5.0 companies** (I5.0 practices). The initial step involves the identification of European companies recognized as I5.0 frontrunners.

Figure 2: Framework model for workforce skills in I5.0 [3]

By identifying organizational practices that promote human centricity, resilience, and sustainability, the objective is to understand implemented structures, associated tasks, technology adoption strategies, and prevailing attitudes. The methodology unfolds through several key phases:

- Preliminary Phase: Identifying I5.0 practices of model companies and assessing the current status of learning ecosystems by evaluating existing I5.0 elements in ongoing learning programs.
- Design the pilots: Details the training activities and the technology integration by means of enhanced Learning Factories for I5.0.
- Evaluation of achievements, feasibility and drawing of generalized conclusions through pilot comparisons.
- Future proof of the interventions for sustained impact.

3. Results & Discussion

Five learning ecosystems - FH Joanneum/I4.0 Platform (AUT), Basque VET Pilot (BC) Smartmakers (NL), Sharehouse (NL), LPK (LT) - , are piloting the methodology for advanced manufacturing training programmes for students, companies and job seekers.²

In the preliminary phase, the project identified the initial status of the learning ecosystems related to I5.0 aspects. The assessment was carried out by comparing to what extent I5.0 practices are implemented in those ecosystems. See table for results (the scores are in a 1-5 scale).

Initial situation (A)	I5.0 score	Human Centricity	Resilience	Sustainability
Learning ecosystem 1	2,2	2,0	2,5	2,0
Learning ecosystem 2	2,5	2,4	2,5	2,5
Learning ecosystem 3	3,0	3,1	2,5	3,5
Learning ecosystem 4	1,7	1,7	1,0	2,3
Learning ecosystem 5	1,9	1,6	1,5	2,8
Average	2,3	2,2	2,0	2,6

² Bridges 5.0 include another 4 pilots in companies, Comau (IT), Infineon (AUT) Mondragon Corporation (BC), Kitron (LT) following the methodology adapted to their needs.

The initial assessment puts the basis to define which I5.0 practices must be improved and to design the training pilots, including the enhanced Learning Factories. Each learning ecosystem sets the priorities, technologies and targets to address.

However, for a more accurate comparison between pilots a further elaboration of the I5.0 practices are necessary. The level of complexity of the interactions among I5.0 dimensions makes the assessment rather vague. This vagueness is accentuated by the fact that the results of the evaluation depend to some extent on the person carrying it out, which reduces objectivity. Furthermore, the organizational aspects that highly influence upon I5.0 adoptions are not always straightforward applicable in education environments.

4. Conclusions & Recommendations

The methodology reveals the potential to formulate training interventions for I5.0 by drawing from successful industrial practices focusing on human-centric, resilience, and sustainability aspects. A selection of I5.0 practices have been utilized to assess the current status of the learning ecosystems involved and to determine the targets for the pilot programs.

Despite the benefits of establishing a common baseline for comparison and extrapolating findings for subsequent work, prudence is necessary due to the subjective nature of the analysis.

Recommendations:

- Better understanding of mechanism used in industry to deploy human centric, resilience and sustainability aspects.
- Explore further integration of I5.0 principles into diverse learning ecosystems.
- Foster ongoing discussions on assessment methods for I5.0 practices.
- Encourage the replication I5.0 practices in Learning Factory settings.

References

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- [2] Bridges5.0 (2023) <https://bridges5-0.eu/>
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